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Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Dhananjay Datta, Bhaskar Sharma (2017), "Impulse Purchase Behavior among the Millennials at Agartala, Tripura, India", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5, (Issue 5, May-2017), pp 01-17

IMPULSE PURCHASE BEHAVIOR AMONG THE MILLENNIALS AT AGARTALA, TRIPURA, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Impulse purchase or impulse buying describes an unplanned decision to buy a product or service, made just before a purchase. This paper is an attempt to understand the consumer impulse buying behavior among the millennials at superstores in Agartala. The impact of various variables like discount offer, various scheme, promotional activities, retail store offer, display of product, behavior of sales person, popularity of product, influence of reference group, income level of customers and festival season, on consumer impulse buying behavior, have been analyzed. The study is based on the primary data collected with the help of structured questionnaire. Data analysis has been done using SPSS software. The statistical analysis method employed in this study is Factor Analysis. The final outcome of the study helps in understanding the factors that affect the impulse purchase or impulse buying behavior of the customers and also the stimuli that triggers impulse buying.

Introduction: An impulse purchase or impulse buying is an unplanned or otherwise spontaneous purchase. Impulse items can be anything, a new product, samples or well-established products at surprising low prices. Parboteeah (2005) stated that impulse purchasing is unplanned, the result of an exposure to a stimulus, and is decided on-the-spot. Impulse buyers start browsing without having a purpose to procure a definite article or visiting certain store. As customers browse, they are exposed to the stimuli, which triggers customers' urge to buy on impulse. When impulse consumers consider the aspiration to purchase, they construct a procure decision with no penetrating for data and information or appraising best possible alternatives. Then, customers may face positive or negative outcomes through the post-purchase assessment after the procure on impulse. In this progression, shoppers are prejudiced by inner and outside things that generate the impulse purchase behavior.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

There are several studies which have indicated the significance of a growing trend towards unplanned purchasing.

- Unplanned purchases are commonly found in drugstores (Vernon, 1950), in supermarkets (Nemours and Wilmington, 1965), departmental stores and discount stores (Kanti, 1975).
- Both men and women were found different with respect to affective process components, including irresistible urge to buy, positive buying emotion, and mood management, and cognitive process components, including cognitive deliberation and unplanned buying with the exception of disregard for the future (Coley, 1999).
- Participants whose resources were depleted, relative to participants whose resources were not depleted, felt stronger urges to buy, were willing to spend more, and actually did spend more money in unanticipated buying situations (Kathleen and Ronald, 2007).

- A pivotal relationship between window display, credit card, promotional activities (discount, free product) and consumer impulse buying behavior was found (Alireza and Hasti, 2011). The study reviewed lot of research report on the research topic and above mentioned few indicates stimuli for impulse purchase from consumer behavioral perspective from various countries. The literatures suggest that Generation-Y or youth around the world exhibit various types of impulse purchase. Hence, the present study gains importance in analyzing the impulse purchase behavior of the youth segment of the population.

Objectives: The primary objective of the study is to understand impulse buying behavior among the millennials at Agartala, Tripura, India. In tune with the primary objective, the following

Secondary objectives were framed:

To examine the factors influencing impulse purchase,

To evaluate the stimuli that triggers impulse buying among the millennials.

METHODOLOGY:

Research Approach

- The approach used for the study will be Survey Method.
- Literature Survey was done and Survey was carried out.

Area chosen for the study: Agartala.

Target Population of the Study

Customers of age groups between 18 years and 35 years.

Sample Size: The sample size consists of 110 respondents.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Primary Data Collection:

A Sample of 110 respondents was selected from the target population, according to researcher's convenience, to conduct the study. The primary data were obtained from the responses of the respondents to the questionnaire designed. The questionnaire consists of close-ended questions. A part of the questionnaire was designed to know the basic details of the respondents.

Secondary Data Collection:

The secondary data were collected by referring manuals, journals and intranet, websites and the final data will be analyzed systematically to achieve the desired result.

Sampling method: A probability sampling procedure, namely, random sampling method has been used for selecting the sample respondents.

Data analysis tools: Descriptive statistical tools like chi-square test and factor analysis has also been applied for the data analysis and also percentage analysis through pie chart and diagrams. The 5 point Likert scale has been used to quantify and analyze the data.

Data analysis:

Socio economic profile results:

Socioeconomic profile of the consumer has great implications for marketers. Customers' personality and demographic or socioeconomic characteristics have been shown to be related to the rate of impulse buying. Among the youth, 47.27% of sample respondents were aged between 19 and 25 years; female respondents constituted 55.45% and the remaining 44.55% were male respondents. A majority of the respondents (60%) were married. The nuclear family type was predominant among the respondents. As far as occupation is concerned, 24% were self-employed, 28% were salaried, 15% were homemakers and the remaining 33% were students. The classification of respondents based on education was: 35% were postgraduates, 32% were undergraduates, 19% had higher secondary education, and the remaining respondents had education till diploma courses. The respondents were classified based on their monthly income. About 35% of the respondents had income below ₹20,000, 43% had income between ₹20,000-30,000, and the remaining 22% of the respondents had income above ₹30,000.

Impulse Purchase Behavior among Youth

The product and brand bought on impulse were analyzed and presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The difference between the products planned for purchase and actually purchased shows the unplanned purchase behavior of the respondents (Table 1). Such differences in product purchased were tested for the youth respondents.

Table 1: Products for Impulse Purchase				
Products	List Planned		Actually Purchased	
	No. of Respondents	Percent	No. of Respondents	Percent
Branded Clothes	18	16.4	24	21.8
Candy	9	12.7	5	4.5
Shoes	14	10	17	15.5
Games Equipment	5	11.3	2	1.8
Flowers	7	14	6	5.5
Music	4	9.3	4	3.6
Food	16	8.7	18	16.4
Interior Decoration	8	10.7	5	4.5
Movies	12	4	14	12.7
Accessories	6	6	6	5.5
Hygiene Articles	6	2	5	4.5
Articles	5	3	4	3.6

Source: Field survey

The youth segment of population has comparatively different tastes and preferences when compared to the consumers of other age groups. The Generation-Y were attracted to buy on impulse, mostly branded clothes (21.8%), shoes (15.5%), food (16.4%), movies (12.7%). The need before purchase and at the time of their actual purchase showed a lot of difference. Some of the additional items purchased did not match with the list planned for purchase. It is seen that branded clothes, shoes, movies and food are purchased more often on impulse. Marketers should therefore focus on such items when attempting to promote impulse purchases.

It is quite obvious from Table 2 that 55.5% of the respondents bought on impulse the brand of product which they have never seen or heard about. About 38.2% of respondents have bought only the familiar brands even in an impulse buying situation. It is observed that consumers more often buy a new brand (which they never tried before) on impulse. Therefore, where applicable, marketers may adopt new brands when trying to trigger impulse purchases.

Brand Familiarity	No. of Respondents	Percentage
New Brand	61	55.5
Familiar Brand	42	38.2
Don't Know	7	6.4

Source: Field survey

STIMULI FOR IMPULSE BUYING AMONG YOUTH

Impulse buying usually occurs owing to both external and internal stimuli. The external stimulus is what both stores and product manufacturers can use to their advantage to encourage impulse buying. How the products are made is not something that the stores can control, which means that the focus should be on the layout of the stores and the knowledge about their consumers instead. The most important thing is to adapt to the consumer and look for solutions in order to encourage a purchase. This means that the staff should have extensive knowledge about the products sold in the store, to be able to emphasize the advantages to the consumer in a way that makes it preferable for the consumers.

The multiple responses on stimuli for impulse buying among youth, as shown in Table 3, indicated that curiosity (12.72%) and inherent need (9.83%) motivated respondents to indulge in impulse buying. The internal stimuli for unplanned purchase were of emotion and hedonic influences. The hedonic needs seek to achieve pleasure from a product. They are more likely to be associated with emotions or fantasies derived from consuming a product. The product promotion incorporating feelings of strong emotion and fashion would lead to pure and unplanned purchase behavior among the female respondents belonging to Generation-Y. The background music played in the store stimulated the respondents (5.20%) to purchase products impulsively. The motivation of salespersons influenced impulse buying (2.89%). The quality of the product motivated 8.09% of the respondents to involve in impulse buying. Many of the respondents agreed that they did impulse buying due to attractive commercials (6.36%). The desire to buy some product motivated 6.94% of the respondents to do impulse purchase. Other factors which stimulated impulse buying among the youth were bargain (4.62%), window display (4.05%) and fashion trends (9.25%). Thus, the stimulus for impulse purchase is created through in-store ambience, with music, knowledgeable salespersons who recommend suitable products to the youth thereby creating desire and curiosity for shopping, through commercials and on the spot promotion.

Variable	No. of Respondents	Percentage*
External Stimuli		
Shopping Environment		
Windows Display	7	4.05
Shopping Experiences	4	2.31
Music	9	5.20
Model	4	2.31
Salespersons		
Attention	6	3.47
Consultation	5	2.89

Marketing Communication		
Discount	12	6.94
Quality	14	8.09
Attention	6	3.47
Design	13	7.51
Commercial	11	6.36
Knowledge	7	4.05
Bargain	8	4.62
Internal Stimuli		
Emotions		
Need	17	9.83
Desire	12	6.94
Hedonic		
Curiosity	22	12.72
Trendy	16	9.25

Note: * This is multiple responses totaling to 173 respondents and accordingly percentage is calculated.

Source: Field survey

Types of Impulse Purchase among Youth

Among department store shoppers, age and socioeconomic status may influence the amount of impulse purchasing (Ballenger *et al.*, 1985). The types of impulse purchase among youth were tested for their association with the socioeconomic profile of the respondents and the occasion of purchase.

Association between Type of Impulse Purchase Behavior and Socioeconomic Profile of the Respondents

The impulse buying behavior was classified into four different types, namely, pure impulse, unplanned, suggestive and reminder (Stern, 1962). In order to understand the dominant type of behavior prevailing among the youth, the socioeconomic profiles of the respondents were associated with the behavior type.

Table 4: Types of Impulse Purchase Behavior Based on Socioeconomic Profile of the Respondents

Variable		Types of Impulse Purchase Behavior									
		Planned		Pure		Suggestive		Reminder		Total	
		1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Age (in years)	19-25	15	29.03	18	35.48	12	22.58	7	12.9	52	100
	26-30	10	26.92	14	38.46	4	11.53	9	23.07	37	100
	Upto 35	9	44.44	5	22.22	4	19.44	3	13.88	21	100
Gender	Male	16	33.33	16	31.88	11	23.19	6	11.59	49	100
	Female	19	30.86	21	34.57	8	13.58	13	20.99	61	100
Marital Status	Single	14	33.33	14	33.33	8	18.52	8	18.52	44	100
	Married	21	31.25	21	32.29	14	20.83	10	15.63	66	100
Occupation	Self-Employed	9	33.33	11	43.33	2	6.67	4	16.67	26	100
	Salary	10	32.46	9	31.17	6	18.18	6	18.18	31	100
	Homemaker	4	25.93	5	29.63	5	29.63	3	14.81	17	100
	Student	14	37.5	11	31.25	7	18.75	5	12.5	36	100
Education	HSC	6	26.92	7	34.66	6	26.92	2	11.54	21	100
	UG	11	31.71	12	34.15	4	12.2	8	21.95	35	100
	PG	14	36.84	13	33.33	7	17.54	5	12.28	39	100
	Diploma	6	40	3	20	3	20	3	20	15	100
Monthly Income (in Rs.)	10,000-20,000	14	37.74	10	24.53	9	22.64	6	15.09	39	100
	20,000-30,000	12	26.15	16	33.85	8	16.92	11	23.08	47	100
	Above 30,000	8	34.38	11	46.88	3	12.5	2	6.25	24	100
Family Type	Joint	10	27.59	15	39.66	5	12.07	8	20.69	38	100
	Nuclear	25	34.78	21	29.35	16	21.74	10	14.13	72	100

Source: Field survey

Note:

Here (1) denotes number of respondents and (2) denotes percentage.

Table 4 shows the different types of impulse buying behavior. The respondents in the age group between 19 and 25 years (35.48%) and between 26 and 30 years (38.46%) exhibited pure impulse buying. Female respondents dominated in pure impulse buying (34.57%) and planned buying behavior (30.86%) due to the marketing stimuli like special offers and got carried away by strong emotions. Male respondents also exhibited planned buying (33.33%), pure impulse buying (31.88%), and suggestive impulse buying (23.19%). Male respondents differ in exhibiting more suggestive impulse buying than female respondents. Married respondents exhibited more pure impulse buying (32.29%), planned buying (31.25%), and suggestive buying (20.83%). The patterns of impulse buying prevailing among respondents who live in nuclear family were

planned impulse buying (34.78%) and pure impulse buying (29.35%). A similar pattern of buying was also noted from the respondents living in joint families. Based on educational attainment, planned (36.84%) and pure impulse (33.33%) buying were noticed among the postgraduate respondents. The salaried respondents exhibited all types of impulse buying behavior. The respondents who are self-employed exhibited pure impulse buying (43.33%) and homemakers (29.63%) exhibited pure and suggestive buying. The students did pure impulse buying predominantly. The respondents with a monthly income of above ₹30,000 exhibited pure impulse buying (46.88%) and planned impulse buying (34.38%). In order to test the association between socioeconomic profile of the respondents and the pattern of impulse buying behavior, the following null hypotheses were tested using chi-square test and results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Association Between Types of Impulse Purchase Behavior and Socioeconomic Profile of the Respondents				
Variable	Chi-Square Value	Degrees of Freedom	Sig. @ 5%	Null Hypothesis
Age	8.108	6	0.230	Accepted
Gender	4.038	3	0.258	Accepted
Marital Status	1.497	3	0.683	Accepted
Education	8.696	1	0.729	Accepted
Employment	6.129	3	0.214	Accepted
Monthly Income	9.272	6	0.727	Accepted
Family Type	4.76	3	0.214	Accepted

H_0 : There is no significant association between the types of impulse purchase behavior of the respondents and their socioeconomic profile.

H_a : There is significant association between the types of impulse purchase behavior of the respondents and their socioeconomic profile.

It is understood from the above results that none of the socioeconomic variables of the respondents is associated with the different types of impulse purchase behavior pattern among the youth. The impulse buying behavior of the youth is associated with variables other than their socioeconomic profile.

Association between Types of Impulse Purchase Behavior of the Respondents and the Occasion of Purchase

Situation of purchase has implications for impulse purchase. Among different types of impulse purchase, the occasion of purchase influences the respondents to decide on a particular type of impulse purchase.

Table 6 reveals spontaneous and immediate purchase behavior prevailing among the respondents. About 6% of the respondents did planned purchase while shopping in leisure. Pure impulse purchases were noticed in shopping soon after returning from work. Suggestive impulse purchases among youth were highly prevailing when the respondents were hungry while shopping. Reminder impulse purchase occurred when the respondents did shopping with their friends. Store layout could be altered beneficially keeping in mind the occasion of shopping by youth. Leisure shopping results in unplanned purchase, pure impulse in a happy state, suggestive impulse purchase when hungry, and reminder impulse when shopping with friends.

Table 6: Types of Impulse Buying Behavior and the Occasion of Purchase

Occasion of Purchase	Planned		Pure		Suggestive		Reminder		Total	
	No. of respondents	Percentage								
Before Work	2	1.82	3	2.73	3	2.73	2	1.82	10	9.09
When Happy	2	1.82	9	8.18	4	3.64	3	2.73	18	16.36
With Friends	4	3.64	2	1.82	1	0.91	4	3.64	11	10.66
In Leisure	7	6.36	2	1.82	1	0.91	1	0.91	11	10.66
When Hungry	4	3.64	5	4.55	4	3.64	2	1.82	15	13.33
After Work	8	7.27	5	4.55	3	2.73	3	2.73	19	16.00
When in Bad Mood	2	1.82	3	2.72	1	0.91	0	0.00	6	6.66
When I Am by Myself	2	1.82	3	2.72	2	1.82	2	1.82	9	9.33
When in a Rush	5	4.55	3	2.72	2	1.82	1	0.91	11	8

Source:
Field
survey

Factors Influencing Impulse Purchase Behavior among Generation-Y

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.843
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Chi-Square	358.227
	Df	210
	Sig.	0.000

In order to have a thorough understanding of the dominant factors influencing unplanned buying behavior among youth, the data collected were subjected to factor analysis. To bring out the underlying factors, Varimax Rotation with Kaiser Normalization was used. The principal component analysis was used for extraction purposes. The criterion for selecting the number of factors was based on eigen value. All those factors which had eigen value more than one were included. On applying Varimax Rotation, nine factors had eigen value i.e., more than one. The KMO and Bartlett’s test was applied to bring out sample adequacy and is highly significant as shown in Table 7, and the factors influencing impulse buying are shown in Table 8.

In order to determine the key factors, a factor loading of 0.6 and above was considered to be significant. The factor one was named as “Trend-setters”, consisting of the variables, “It is important to be a fashion leader” (0.761), “I am aware of fashion trends and want to be one of the first to try them” (0.679) and “I am confident in my ability to be recognized with fashion trends” (0.622). Factor two was named “Fashion Appearance”, consisting of the variables “I am the first to try a new fashion: many people regard me as being a fashion leader” (0.715) and “For an active lifestyle, I need a wide variety of clothes” (0.612). Factor three was named “Fashion-related Activities”, consisting of the variables “I spend lot of money on clothes and accessories” (0.746), “I spend more time in fashion-related activities and I’m always well-dressed” (0.682). Fourth factor was named “Self-image”, consisting of the variables “to get ahead, one has to dress well (0.703)” and “personality is reflected in what I wear (0.639)”. Factor five was named as “Symbol of Good Life”, which included the variables “Wearing good clothes is part of leading a good life” (0.749). Factor six was named “Not a Fashion Leader”, consisting of the variables “I buy clothes regardless of the current fashion” (0.709). Factor seven “Instant Gratification” consisted of the variables that state that the youth want everything instantly and do not have the tendency to postpone any purchases and “Just do it, describes their way of buying things” (0.824). Factor eight “No Prior Thinking before buying” consists of the variables “unplanned buying without prior

thinking" (0.796). Factor nine named "Impulse buying," included the variable when the respondent feels like buying things on the spur of the moment" (0.817). All these nine factors together explained 63.11% of influences in the impulse purchase decision of the youth respondents. Of all the variables, the highest communality value of 0.756 was noted for the respondent impulse, reckless purchase about what they intend to buy. The youth segment of population could be targeted with suitable marketing mix by bringing in new fashion trends, promotion, self-image and stimuli for instant gratification.

Factors influencing impulse buying among the respondents										
Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Communalities
X1	0.761	– 0.023	0.176	0.255	– 0.075	0.033	– 0.075	0.077	0.081	0.63
X2	0.679	0.145	– 0.179	– 0.218	– 0.066	– 0.129	0.155	– 0.033	– 0.058	0.7
X3	0.622	– 0.267	– 0.065	0.174	0.103	0.286	0.081	– 0.022	0.176	0.686
X4	0.531	0.329	0.246	– 0.001	0.298	0.024	– 0.286	– 0.190	– 0.170	0.75
X5	0.027	0.715	– 0.064	0.089	– 0.072	0.106	– 0.020	0.099	– 0.062	0.611
X6	0.006	0.612	– 0.225	0.126	0.044	0.191	0.172	0.012	0.096	0.556
X7	– 0.172	0.376	– 0.268	0.254	– 0.011	– 0.299	0.284	– 0.214	0.129	0.666
X8	– 0.062	– 0.133	0.746	– 0.163	0.04	– 0.040	0.092	0.013	0.096	0.568
X9	0.084	– 0.081	0.682	0.209	– 0.150	0.081	0.107	– 0.066	– 0.100	0.554
X10	0.03	0.098	0.048	0.703	0.013	0.048	0.237	– 0.059	– 0.074	0.593
X11	0.126	0.21	– 0.046	0.639	0.149	– 0.143	– 0.189	0.084	– 0.014	0.686
X12	– 0.094	– 0.099	– 0.123	0.128	0.749	0.15	0.076	– 0.182	0.115	0.518
X13	0.085	– 0.163	0.051	0.296	0.596	– 0.353	– 0.178	0.145	0.002	0.623
X14	0.078	0.281	– 0.023	– 0.205	0.595	– 0.009	0.254	0.193	– 0.215	0.657
X15	0.02	0.08	–	–	–	0.70	–	0.083	–	0.674

		8	0.013	0.175	0.004	9	0.128		0.052	
X_{16}	0.051	0.145	0.052	0.161	0.009	0.671	0.298	0.019	–0.028	0.54
X_{17}	0.048	0.061	0.193	0.055	0.099	0.076	0.824	0.075	0.056	0.578
X_{18}	–0.105	–0.014	–0.191	0.113	0.069	0.153	0.004	0.796	0.183	0.71
X_{19}	0.109	0.17	0.216	–0.152	–0.109	–0.057	0.128	0.637	–0.354	0.626
X_{20}	0.074	0.007	–0.029	–0.137	–0.023	–0.063	0.11	0.021	0.817	0.574
X_{21}	0.03	0.467	0.338	0.199	0.037	–0.072	–0.222	–0.048	0.485	0.756
Eigenvalue	1.822	1.702	1.538	1.503	1.461	1.409	1.305	1.262	1.262	–
Total	8.676	8.103	7.322	7.158	6.959	6.711	6.213	6.01	5.962	–
Cumulative	8.676	16.78	24.101	31.26	38.219	44.93	51.142	57.152	63.114	–
Note: Variables X1 ...Xn represents the statements listed in the questionnaire at serial number 6 (See Appendix).										

Graph 15: Major factors influencing impulse buying

Conclusion: Impulse purchase or impulse buying describes an unplanned decision to buy a product or service, made just before a purchase. Generation-Y is very susceptible to impulse buying and the marketer needs to build their strategies accordingly. From the research it was found that Instant gratification, No prior thinking before buying, Trend setters, Impulse buying were among the major factors that influenced impulse buying. Also the external stimuli that mostly triggered impulse buying among the millennials were quality and design of the products and the internal stimuli were need, curiosity and trendy. The findings of the study are useful to the retailers to improve their merchandise assortment and shopping environment, including store displays, to trigger

impulse purchase. In a highly competitive environment, with the growth of hyper marts and super marts, it would be useful to examine impulse buying behavior among the youth.

Suggestions:

- Marketers may adopt new brands when trying to trigger impulse purchases.
- Marketers can give more focus on branded clothes, shoes, movies and food as they trigger the maximum impulse purchase.
- The youth segment of population could be targeted with suitable marketing mix by bringing in new fashion trends, promotion, self-image and stimuli for instant gratification.

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Appendix
Questionnaire

Profile of the Respondents

1. Name (optional) :
2. Gender : Male Female
3. Age (in years) :
4. Educational Qualification : High School Graduate Postgraduate Diploma
5. Employment : Self-Employment Salaried Homemaker Student
6. Monthly Income of Family : Below ₹10,000 ₹10,000-20,000 ₹20,000-30,000
 ₹30,000-40,000 ₹40,000-50,000 ₹50,000 and Above
7. Marital Status : Single Married
8. Family Type : Nuclear Joint

2. Unplanned Purchase Behavior of the Respondents

1. Your latest impulse purchase was
 Planned Pure Impulse Suggestion-based Reminded of Product
2. When do you do impulse purchase most?
 Before work After work
 When I am happy When I am in bad mood When I am with friends
 When I am by myself When I have time to spare When I am in a rush
 When I am hungry
3. Motivation to do impulse purchase comes from
 Need Desire Curiosity Trendy
 Music Model Commercial Knowledge
 Quality Design Bargain Attention to Commercials
 Windows Display Shopping Experiences

SalesPromotion techniques Consultation with Sales Personnel

4. Tick the products you planned prior and bought on impulse.

Products	List Planned	Actually Purchased
Food		
Movies		

Music		
Branded Clothes		
Shoes		
Games Equipment		
Candy		
Hygiene Articles		
Flower		
Interior Decoration		
Accessories		
Other Articles (specify)		

5. The brand of product bought on each unplanned purchase is

New Brand Familiar Brand Do Not Know

Statement	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
1. It is important for me to be a fashion leader.					
2. I am aware of fashion trends and want to be one of the first to try them.					
3. I am confident in my ability to recognize fashion trends.					
4. One of the most important ways I have of expressing my individuality.					
5. I am the first one to try new fashion: therefore, many people regard me as being a fashion leader.					
6. Because of my active lifestyle, I need a wide variety of articles.					
7. I always buy at least one outfit of the latest fashion.					
8. I spend a lot of money on clothes and accessories purchase.					
9. I spend a lot of time on fashion-related activities; it is important to be well-dressed.					
10. If you want to get ahead, you have to dress well.					
11. What you think of yourself is reflected by what you wear.					
12. Wearing good clothes is part of leading a good life.					
13. I receive suggestion about what to wear from fashion experts.					
14. Fashion is just a way to get more money from the consumer.					

15. I buy articles, regardless of current fashion.					
16. I often buy things spontaneously.					
17. “Just do it” describes the way I buy things.					
18. I often buy things without thinking.					
19. “Buy now, think about it later” describes me.					
20. Sometimes I feel like buying things on the spur of the moment.					
21. Sometimes I am a bit reckless about what I buy.					